

File name: result_1
Author: Bartosz Bossy
Type of file: png (uneditable), fig (editable)
Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7962028>
Size: png 36 KB, fig 27 KB
Created: 15.12.2022
Tool: MATLAB
Generated using: freshness.m (<https://zenodo.org/record/7962007>)

File name: freshness
Author: Bartosz Bossy
Type of file: m
Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7962007>
Size: 6 KB
Created: 14.12.2022
Tool: MATLAB

File name: channel
Author: Bartosz Bossy
Type of file: mat
Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7962007>
Size: 21 KB
Created: 19.03.2016
Tool: MATLAB
